

ENER GIZE

SUPPORTING THE CLEAN ENERGY
TRANSITION OF EUROPEAN BUSINESSES

D6.7 Report on communication and dissemination actions

ENERGIZE

SUPPORTING THE CLEAN ENERGY
TRANSITION OF EUROPEAN BUSINESSES

D6.7 – Report on Communication & Dissemination actions

Authors:

Claudia BRIONGOS, Segis VERDAGUER, Olga BARRACHINA (ESTRATS)

February, 2026 (M20) - WP6, D6.7

Co-funded by
the European Union

Co-funded by the European Union, under Grant Agreement n° 101167570. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Technical References

Project Acronym	ENERGIZE
Project Title	SUPPORTING THE CLEAN ENERGY TRANSITION OF EUROPEAN BUSINESSES

Deliverable No. & Title	D6.7 – Report on Communication & Dissemination actions
Type of deliverable	R (document, report)
Dissemination Level	PU
Work Package	WP6 – WP Sustainability replication, exploitation plan
Lead beneficiary	PARTNER 3 (ESTRATS)
Contributing beneficiary(ies)	PARTNER 6 (FEDARENE)
Due date of deliverable	28 February 2026
Actual submission date	

Authors	Claudia BRIONGOS, Segis VERDAGUER, Olga BARRACHINA (ESTRATS)
Contributors	Diana Bosfy (FEDARENE), Anna Arias (IRIS)

Versions

Version	Date	Changes	Edited by
0.1	19/01/2026	Initial draft	Claudia BRIONGOS
0.2	24/01/2026	Update of Indicators	Segis VERDAGUER
0.3	10/02/2026	Internal revision	Olga BARRACHINA
0.4	23/02/2026	Revision by partners	Diana BOSFY

Content

1	Introduction	8
2	Communication and Dissemination	9
2.1	Overall objectives	9
2.2	Key principles	9
3	Target audience	11
3.1	Priority Target Groups	11
3.2	Tailored strategy to Target Groups	12
4	Communication, dissemination and engagement channels	14
4.1	Promotional material	14
4.2	Project website	14
4.3	Project videos	15
4.4	Social media accounts	15
4.4.1	<i>LinkedIn</i>	15
4.4.2	<i>X (formerly Twitter)</i>	16
4.4.3	<i>Instagram</i>	16
4.4.4	<i>YouTube</i>	16
4.4.5	<i>Share with official LIFE channels</i>	16
4.5	Press releases and newsletters	17
5	Monitoring	18
5.1	What to monitor	18
5.2	Communication and dissemination KPIs	18
6	Dissemination of results & open access	20
6.1	Obligation to disseminate results	20
6.2	Information on EU funding – Obligation and right to use the LIFE emblem	20
6.3	Disclaimer excluding EU responsibility	20
7	Specific communication actions performed the first 20 months.	21
8	Annex 1 – Communication & Dissemination activities performed	22

Executive Summary

The ENERGIZE project is co-funded by the European Commission through the LIFE Clean Energy Transition program. ENERGIZE aims to demonstrate the potential of cooperative energy models in industrial zones across the EU. These initiatives face considerable challenges - especially in governance, legal frameworks and financial sustainability which ENERGIZE aims to overcome. It will promote energy collaboration through active engagement, capacity building, and the creation of a dedicated digital hub to serve as a support tool. This approach will foster renewable energy projects, resource efficiency, and circularity within these communities.

This document is the third release of the ENERGIZE's Communication, Dissemination and Engagement plan, which updates the communication, dissemination and engagement strategy already fixed in the 2nd version of the document, and the corresponding activities to spread the knowledge generated during ENERGIZE project and engage with key stakeholders.

Further updates will be provided as the project progresses.

List of Tables

Table 3-1 – Priority Target Groups of ENERGIZE Communication and Dissemination strategy	11
Table 3-2 – Other relevant Target Groups (2 nd level) of ENERGIZE Communication and Dissemination strategy	12
Table 3-3– Specific target audience communication, dissemination and engagement messages and channels	12
Table 4-1– LIFE main hashtags	16
Table 5-1– Communication and dissemination activities KPIs	18
Table 7-1 – Communication and dissemination activities performed the first 20 months of the project	21
Table 8-1 3 rd Newsletter	29

List of Figures

Figure 2-1– Principal schema of communication and dissemination activities	10
Figure 5-1– Principles of monitoring and evaluation	18
Figure 8-1– “Home” and “Resources” sections (partial view), and Google Analytics results	23
Figure 8-2– Pilot region’s versions	24
Figure 8-3– ENERGIZE poster	24
Figure 8-4– Frame of the constitutional video	25
Figure 8-5– Frame of the several short videos	26
Figure 8-6– samples of LinkedIn posts	27
Figure 8-7– samples of Instagram posts	27
Figure 8-8 2 nd Newsletter	28

Abbreviations and acronyms

ABBREVIATION OR ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
CA	Consortium Agreement
CDEP	Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Plan
EC	Energy Communities
ESCO	Energy Services Companies
ET	Energy Transition
GA	Grant Agreement
IEC	Industrial Energy Communities
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LIFE CET	LIFE Clean Energy Transition
PA	Public Authority
PPs	Project partners
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
TG	Target Groups
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

The Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Plan (CDEP) is part of the activities of Work Package 6, the “Task 6.1 – Communication and Dissemination of ENERGIZE Project”, centralizes most of the coordination and implementation of the project’s communication and dissemination activities. Task 6.1 consists of different subtasks:

- T6.1.1: Communication, dissemination and engagement plan and coordination
- T6.1.2: Communication material and tools, which includes:
 - Project brand and visual identity
 - Landing webpage and blog
 - Project brochure
 - Communication videos
- T6.1.3: Dissemination activities and communication campaigns, which includes:
 - Social media
 - Press releases and newsletter
 - Communication campaigns
 - Site visits
 - Participation in public events
 - Networking with other LIFE projects
 - Final ENERGIZE International Workshop

The CDEP will constitute the core document outlining the activities at the basis of the project’s dissemination and communication activities, and will set up and manage an effective communication and dissemination strategy to guarantee the professional and public coverage of the project results, and to maximise the visibility of the project results and actions to all the stakeholders and target audience.

It will be subject to revision every 12 months in order to fine tune the dissemination, communication and engagement objectives with project results, and include potential new communication tools and targets that may appear over time. Thus, this 2nd CDEP will aim at selecting which results should be given priority and how they need to be communicated within the second year of the project.

Complementarily to this CDEP, the ENERGIZE project has foreseen the development of a Stakeholder Engagement Strategy (D5.1, by month 12), which complements the activities planned within this deliverable.

2 Communication and Dissemination

2.1 Overall objectives

All communication and dissemination activities have been designed to impact the specific segmented target audience of the project. The main objectives of communication, dissemination and engagement activities are:

- Reducing the knowledge gap for the actors involved.
- Facilitating and easing the establishment of industrial energy communities and clusters.
- Supporting optimal conditions and solutions for the replication and exploitation of the project outcomes.
- Consolidating the project visibility among the industry sector and stakeholders at EU level to enhance awareness.
- Guaranteeing the scientific and public coverage of the project results.

These objectives are closely aligned with the LIFE Programme Communication rules, which highlights the need to communicate the benefits of EU funded projects to the whole society.

2.2 Key principles

The communication activities will be grouped and planned at four levels, according to their communication objectives:

Pilot territories level

This level focuses on communication and marketing to ensure the deployment of the ENERGIZE project within pilot regions. It aims to engage stakeholders and raise awareness among industries and public authorities. The communication strategy consists of communicating information about the specific pilot case, its milestones, progress and news. The project website, social media and local press are the key communication channels. Local language will be prioritized.

Supra-regional and national level

Communication and marketing to ensure the scale-up of ENERGIZE pilots to the whole region/country, depending on the pilot case, and inform stakeholders, other industries, public authorities (local, regional and national) and general public. The communication is focused on explaining the project and its potential scale-up to neighbour regions around pilot cases, including project progress and news. The

project website and social media are the key communication channels. Local language and English are used.

Replication at a wide EU level

At this level, broader communication, to all EU stakeholders, to maximize the replication of ENERGIZE methodologies and the expansion at EU level of the ENERGIZE Digital Hub (the “One-Stop-Shop” interface for accessing project outputs and for hosting a pan-European virtual stakeholder community linked to energy cooperation). The communication explains the project’s contributions to energy transition (ET) and highlight achievements from the pilot territories. This will encourage industries, clusters, and regions across the EU to participate in the replication phase and adopt some of the project results. The website and social media are the key communication channels. English language is prioritized.

Mainstream level

This level aims to communicate project objectives, progress and results with a wider audience and various target groups throughout the EU. This communication level includes all general communication activities and channels.

Figure 2-1– Principal schema of communication and dissemination activities

3 Target audience

The target audience of ENERGIZE communication, dissemination and engagement activities includes all the key stakeholders identified as potential contributors to enhance the achievement of the project's goals in terms of cooperative energy model capacity building, implementation and replicability. Each of these stakeholders plays a crucial role in facilitating energy cooperation and collaborative approaches in various contexts, from value chains to local communities and industrial parks. They have the potential to make valuable contributions in terms of providing specialized knowledge, offering access to relevant networks or resources, and participating in co-creation and collaborative activities that align with the project's mission, among other contributions.

3.1 Priority Target Groups

The overall success of the ENERGIZE+ project fundamentally relies on the expertise and efforts of the consortium members, as well as the engagement and participation of the target groups, both within the project pilots and beyond.

The identification of target groups considers the importance of the different key actors for the successful development of the project. In this regard, the most relevant and priority target groups for ENERGIZE project are:

Table 3-1 – Priority Target Groups of ENERGIZE Communication and Dissemination strategy

TG	Target Group	Importance
TG1	Local and regional industrial parks and clusters	They play a central role in energy cooperation and can provide valuable insights into local energy needs and potential collaboration opportunities.
TG2	Industry associations and chambers of commerce	They represent the interests of businesses within specific sectors and can facilitate broader industry adoption of clean energy practices.
TG3	Energy agencies, public authorities (e.g. focused on energy policies)	They set and hold expertise in the policies and regulatory frameworks that can hinder or support clean energy initiatives and can provide valuable data and insights for project analysis.
TG4	Financial institutions, aggregators, investors	They play a crucial role in securing funding for energy efficiency and renewable energy projects, providing necessary capital for successful launch and rollout of energy communities.

Furthermore, ENERGIZE also targets any potential contributor to enhance the achievement of the project's goals in terms of cooperative energy model capacity building, set up and replicability, such as:

Table 3-2 – Other relevant Target Groups (2nd level) of ENERGIZE Communication and Dissemination strategy

TG	Target Group	Importance
TG5	Energy Services stakeholders: ESCOs, energy consultants, utility companies, RES providers & installers, HVAC providers & installers	They specialise in renewable and/or energy efficiency solutions, offering valuable expertise in project implementation.
TG6	Local communities, residents, general public	Their buy-in and support are critical for the successful deployment of energy communities.

3.2 Tailored strategy to Target Groups

The communication, dissemination and engagement activities are tailored to the different target groups, to maximise the efficiency of the action. In particular, the key message and specific channels for the different audiences include:

Table 3-3– Specific target audience communication, dissemination and engagement messages and channels

TG	Key objectives, specific channels
TG1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Obj: Highlight the benefits of participating in the project, such as reduced operating costs, improved sustainability, new tailored services.
TG2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Obj: Conduct targeted outreach and workshops to foster engagement. ● Obj: Showcase the State-of-the-Art analysis of energy cooperation landscape, to promote synergies and collaboration between different organisations and entities. ● Key channels: workshops, webinars, LinkedIn
TG3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Obj: Highlight benefits of fostering and replicating the project for the territory, such as enhancement of Energy Transition and reduction of emissions. To engage in dialogue to ensure alignment of project activities with regional energy policies. ● Obj: Showcase the State-of-the-Art analysis of energy cooperation landscape, to promote synergies and collaboration between different organisations and entities. ● Key channels: workshops, webinars, LinkedIn, X
TG4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Obj: Showcase new business models and services, opportunities for financial operators. Promote partnerships to explore funding options and new business models. ● Key channels: workshops, LinkedIn
TG5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Obj: Showcase new business models and services, new opportunities for promotion of RES. Promote the development of new energy efficiency measures.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Obj: Showcase the State-of-the-Art analysis of energy cooperation landscape, to promote synergies and collaboration between different organisations and entities.● Key channels: webinars, LinkedIn, X, Instagram
TG6	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Obj: Awareness raising on Energy Transition and energy communities.● Key channels: LinkedIn, X, Instagram

4 Communication, dissemination and engagement channels

4.1 Promotional material

The promotional materials consist of:

- A general roll up banner in English, to present the project in any stand or side event.
- A detailed roll up in English, including details on the objectives, pilots and expected impact.
- A project flyer -postcard format- printed in the five project languages, describing the project objectives, the proposed methodology and the expected results.
- A project brochure in English, highlighting the project approach and key project achievements.

4.2 Project website

As a key channel for interaction with the engaged stakeholders of the project and the selected target groups, a project website has been created. It will be the key tool to communicate and disseminate information about the progress and the results achieved by the project. The website includes a repository of information, considered as a lively tool with continuously updated content (news and press releases, original articles and interviews, posts of project-related news from external sources, cross-linking).

The website is available in English and the national languages of pilots (German, Italian, Czech and Catalan). In addition, each project partner will create a special section on its own website in its national language, describing briefly the project and dedicated to the promotion of its results.

In addition to the project landing page, project partners (PPs) will need to present the project in their own websites or social media accounts. This should include, at least:

- Project summary.
- Project logo.
- List of participants.
- Contact details
- European flag and funding statement
- Project results (when available)

4.3 Project videos

Communication videos are a key way to raise awareness on the positive impact of energy communities on the framework of ENERGIZE project. These videos aim to raise awareness and encourage public authorities to adopt the project's outcomes.

Several videos are being created or will be created, in close cooperation with pilot partners, in particular:

- 1 constitutional video (2 minutes length) explaining the project approach and expected impacts, already produced at M8.
- 1 replicability video (2 minutes length) addressing project results and key outcomes, to be produced at M30.
- 10 short video clips (15" length) sharing engaging content (e.g. infographics, factsheets and testimonials) to foster adoption of project solutions.

4.4 Social media accounts

Social media represents another essential channel for mainstream communication as well as specific target audience engagement. Specific ENERGIZE profiles have been developed in different channels.

ESTRATS is the main responsible for managing the project's social media accounts but all ENERGIZE partners are encouraged to widen the coverage of the project through their own social media channels. Their support is of high importance to inform ESTRATS about events and developments on one hand, and to increase the audience by promoting and participating in the different social networks on the other hand.

The key parameters of the ENERGIZE project's social media strategy are:

- Proactive Content Planning: Planning the communication content at least 21 days in advance, so providing a communication calendar.
- Consistent Publishing Schedule: Publishing at least twice a week is expected.
- Personalized and Impactful Messaging: Writing in a more personal way and using impactful messages to better engage the general public.
- High-Quality Visual Content: Using interesting and good quality pictures to ensure content is suitable for different channels.

4.4.1 LinkedIn

LinkedIn is the most used platform among ENERGIZE target groups, therefore it is one of the most relevant tools for the communication, dissemination and engagement strategy. It is used to target almost all the target groups (TG1 to TG5). Regular publications are published, around 4-8 per month on average, with short information about the project activities or outcomes. During the second half of the project, longer articles to highlight specific project results will be published regularly.

LinkedIn handle: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/energizcommunity>

4.4.2 X (formerly Twitter)

Public authorities and individuals are still very present in this social media channel, so ENERGIZE wanted to use it as a relevant communication channel with TG3 as well as TG5 and TG6. X handle created : <https://x.com/energizecom>

However, it was decided at M6 that the communication and dissemination through X of ENERGIZE project was not working favourably, and that the algorithm was not allowing a good communication of the project. The Consortium decided to stop publishing in X.

4.4.3 Instagram

The audience reached by Instagram focuses more on the general public (TG6), but also on providers and installers of HVAC, RES, etc (TG5). ENERGIZE feeds this channel with very visual posts, with catchy images and/or videos, as well as stories for specific occasions (e.g. project meetings, and specific achievements).

Instagram handle: <https://www.instagram.com/energizecommunity/>

4.4.4 YouTube

YouTube is a very important communication tool for ENERGIZE. It works as a visual repository of the videos generated by the project, including not only the ENERGIZE produced videos (see section 4.3) but also those public webinars and workshop that have been recorded, so that everybody has access to them if they missed the date where the webinar or workshop took place.

Youtube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/@EnergizecommunityLIFE>

4.4.5 Share with official LIFE channels

ENERGIZE also shares news and stories about project with the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) through their own social media channels, in particular:

- [LinkedIn](#): @LIFEprogramme
- [Twitter](#): @LIFEprogramme
- [Instagram](#): @LIFEprogramme

Furthermore, all publications related to the project should consider these LIFE main hashtags:

Table 4-1– LIFE main hashtags

General	Climate and Energy
#LIFEprogramme	#EnergyTransition
#LIFEproject	#CleanEnergyEU
#LIFEprojects	#ClimateNeutralEU

	#EU2050
--	---------

Finally, highly relevant communication material (such as press releases, videos, or high relevant news) are shared with CINEA communication team by email (CINEA-COMMUNICATION-LIFE@ec.europa.eu) to enhance its visibility.

4.5 Press releases and newsletters

Good press coverage is essential to increase the long-term visibility and impact of the project.

A total of at least six press releases will be produced and distributed throughout the project, particularly when milestones or high interest outcomes are reached. They will be written in English, and distributed to a wide EU audience through the website, social media channels, EU-wide multipliers such as Build Up platform or similar. They will also be submitted to the LIFE+ Communication Team for potential dissemination through LIFE channels.

ENERGIZE will also publish a total of 6 newsletter in English, every 6 months. Each one will include the most relevant news from the previous period, as well as any update from PPs. These newsletters will be distributed to web registered users, and will also be available through the project website and LinkedIn channel. Furthermore, PPs will be encouraged to include the newsletters in their own communications to maximize reach.

5 Monitoring

5.1 What to monitor

It is essential to understand the audience that has been reached by the project, both in quantitative and qualitative parameters. The reactions generated by the project and the level of satisfaction of the audience are crucial to better focus the following communication actions.

Monitoring activities will follow next scheme:

Figure 5-1– Principles of monitoring and evaluation

5.2 Communication and dissemination KPIs

Next tables include the means of evaluation of the different communication and dissemination activities. The related KPIs are the objectives at the end of the project (M36) as well as the real values monitored up to the 20. January. 2026. All the indicators are on track, considering the expected planning of the activities.

Table 5-1– Communication and dissemination activities KPIs

COMMUNICATION AREA	KPIs	M36	M19
PROJECT WEBSITE	Number of unique visitors	2000+	2000+
	Number of page views	7500+	7500+
SOCIAL MEDIA	Number of followers	+50/quarter	295
	Average publications per month	15	14

VIDEOS	Number of short videos	10	13
	Number of views / reach of short videos	200+	4406
	Number of long videos	2	9
	Number of views / reach of long videos	400+	939
NEWSLETTER	Number of publications	6	2
	Number of reach / impressions / interactions	200+	256
PRESS RELEASES	Number of publications	6	3
AWARENESS RAISING CAMPAIGNS	Number of awareness raising campaigns	3	--
	Number of reach / impressions / interactions	3000+	--
CONFERENCES & EVENTS	Number of participated events	10	2
	Number of events organised by the project	1	--
	Number of attendants in organised events	50	--
SITE VISITS	Number of site visits	3	1
	Number of attendees	60+	20
CLUSTERING	Number of similar projects approached	6	2
ENERGIZE DIGITAL HUB	Number of registered users	200+	--
ENERGIZE NETWORK	Number of registered professional members to the project subscription list	200+	--

6 Dissemination of results & open access

6.1 Obligation to disseminate results

Dissemination (Grant Agreement – article 17) is a separate obligation. In that sense, each beneficiary must “disseminate” its results as soon as possible by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means, unless it goes against their legitimate interests. This does not change the obligation to protect results, confidentiality obligations, security obligations, or the obligation to protect personal data.

6.2 Information on EU funding – Obligation and right to use the LIFE emblem

Any communication activities (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant **must include**:

- a) The LIFE Programme flag. High resolution emblems can be found here:
https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/programmes/life/communication-and-gdpr-rules_en
- b) The following statement:
Co-funded by the European Union, under Grant Agreement N° 101167570.

6.3 Disclaimer excluding EU responsibility

Whenever using the funding logo (LIFE programme flag, EU logo, etc), this disclaimer is being used:

Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

➤ Specific communication actions performed the first 20 months.

Here is a table summarizing the communication actions performed during the first 20 months of the project. The several actions focused on setting up the channels and structure of communication, to focus later on raising awareness, engaging key stakeholders, and promoting the project's outcomes across targeted channels. Moving forward, efforts will concentrate on ensuring consistent visibility, strengthening collaborations, and supporting the uptake of ENERGIZE solutions through strategic communication on both local and international levels.

Table 7-1 – Communication and dissemination activities performed the first 20 months of the project

ACTION	DEADLINE
Visual identity and project brand	M3
First operative version of the ENERGIZE landing webpage	M4
Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Plan	M5
Project flyer	M6
Project roll up	M6
Initial set of communication and dissemination material	M6
1 st ENERGIZE newsletter	M6
Identification of sister projects for clustering	M8
1 st ENERGIZE press release	M10
Production of ENERGIZE constitutional video	M10
Project reference in partners' websites	M15
Update of the "Resources" section of ENERGIZE website and Zenodo repository	M16
13 short videos	M13 - M20
Social Media – continue uploading content	M13 – M20
3 newsletters	M13, M19
3 press releases	M13 – M19
1 communication campaigns	M15-M19
Definition of collaboration framework with first sister projects	M18

Clustering with to 2 sister projects	M12
--------------------------------------	-----

8 Annex 1 – Communication & Dissemination activities performed

This section lists the communication and dissemination activities covered from M1-M20 timeline.

M4 – Project website (D6.2)

The project website has been created following the planned timeline. It’s available at www.energizecommunity.eu.

The ENERGIZE website has been designed to be user-friendly and easy to use, with a smooth transition between the different sections and some transversal functionalities (e.g. social networks, contact form, subscription to newsletter, news, languages) that are present in different sections.

Figure 8-1– “Home” and “Resources” sections (partial view), and Google Analytics results

M6 – project flyer (D6.2)

The project flyer has been designed following the proposed timeline.

The flyer has been created in English and the national languages of the four ENERGIZE demo sites.

Figure 8-2– Pilot region’s versions

M6 – project poster

A specific poster and a project roll-up have been designed for increasing the project visibility at fairs and conferences, or for other project events. The poster provides a clear and simple introduction to the project, showcasing social media channels and involved partners.

Figure 8-3– ENERGIZE poster

M6 – 1st newsletter released

The first ENERGIZE newsletter has been released by January 2025, with a summary of the most relevant news of the project. The current number of subscriptions to the newsletter being still small, the newsletter has also been directly distributed to the project partners (to include it on their own newsletters) as well as through LinkedIn, X and the project website.

M10 – Constitutional video (D6.4)

The ENERGIZE constitutional video has been produced following the planned timeline. The 72 seconds length video, available at the ENERGIZE Youtube channel, focuses on the project goals and future outcomes to increase the interest of industries and businesses into the project activities.

Figure 8-4– Frame of the constitutional video

M10 – Short videos

ENERGIZE team has been producing a set of short videos from different activities.

On one hand, the constitutional video has been designed to be divided and presented in 3 different short videos presenting the current situation (phase 1), the challenge (phase 2) and the solution (phase 3). These 20 seconds videos have been already designed, and an ongoing promotion through Social Media channels is being undertaken, in particular LinkedIn, to maximise the project visibility.

Furthermore, several short videos from the partners have been already promoted, highlighting their different roles and points of views regarding the ENERGIZE project.

All these and the forthcoming short videos will be promoted mainly through social media channels, as well as the Youtube shorts section.

Figure 8-5– Frame of the several short videos

M2-M20 – Social media: LinkedIn & Instagram

The ENERGIZE actions include the creation of a LinkedIn “project page” , together with X and Instagram accounts, which centralise all the social media communication activities. More than 200 followers have been activated during the 1st year of the project, considering both platforms. Due to the direction and inconsistent policy taken by X in recent months ENERGIZE partners have agreed to shift their communication regarding ENERGIZE project efforts to LinkedIn and Instagram.

During the first 20 months, the communication activities have been mainly focused on information about the project objectives, and general awareness raising on the need to enhance energy cooperatives in industrial areas.

Figure 8-6— samples of LinkedIn posts

Figure 8-7— samples of Instagram posts

M13-M20 – Publication of press releases

3 press releases have been published during the last 6 months: Insights from existing Energy Cooperation Initiatives in Urban-Industrial areas, Spain’s First Industrial Renewable Energy Community, How INKOBAs Sterngartl turns Companies into a Community. The press releases have also been directly distributed to the project partners as well as through LinkedIn, X and the project website.

M14 – 2nd newsletter released

ENERGIZE second newsletter has been released on August 2025 and it highlights the active participation in key European events—Barcelona, Paris, and Brussels—and share major project milestones, including the publication of key deliverables on Industrial Parks and Energy Communities and the launch of the ENERGIZE introductory video.

ENERGIZE Insights: Boosting Industrial Energy Cooperation Across Europe

In our second newsletter, we highlight ENERGIZE’s active participation in key European events—Barcelona, Paris, and Brussels—and share major project milestones, including the publication of key deliverables on Industrial Parks and Energy Communities and the launch of the ENERGIZE introductory video.

2nd Project Meeting

In February we had our 2nd Project Meeting!

All project partners met in Paris to share and discuss about the great progress done during last months and debate around the approach to follow during next year! 😊

ENERGIZE at the LIFE Contractors Meeting

In April 2025, we had the pleasure of joining fellow LIFE Clean Energy Transition projects at the “Industry & Business Contractors Meeting”, in Brussels. This event, organised by CINEA, was a fantastic opportunity to:

- ✦ Connect with other projects driving Industrial Decarbonisation.
- ✦ Share our vision for Energy Communities in industrial zones.
- ✦ Learn from EU Policy updates and best practices.

Figure 8-8 2nd Newsletter

M19– 3rd newsletter released

ENERGIZE 3rd Newsletter was released in January 2026. It focused on the activities performed until its midpoint. Informing about the 3rd Consortium Meeting in Linz, and the award won by our pilot “Manresa Il-lumina” as a model for industrial energy communities across Europe.

[View this email in your browser](#)

ENERGIZE: Halfway to Impact!

The ENERGIZE project has arrived to its midpoint with major wins on the ground and in policy. Our Catalan pilot, Manresa Il-lumina, is now an award-winning model for industrial energy communities across Europe. Following a productive 3rd Consortium Meeting in Linz, we have solidified our roadmap for the next phase. We have also contributed to IWG meetings and helped local businesses navigate their decarbonization journey at GRID Granollers' Decarbonization Day.

European Recognition for Pioneer Industrial

Energy Community

Manresa Il-lumina, Energize pilot project in Catalonia, has been chosen among 10 of the best project in the Innovation in Politics Awards 2025! This project, led by the Associació d'Empresaris de Bufalvent, showcases a truly pioneering model of an industrial energy community in Manresa, Catalonia.

Their collaborative approach is connecting multiple industrial park companies to produce and consume local, sustainable, solar energy, proving that collective action can drive an efficient hashtag#EnergyTransition where no business is left behind. This is exactly the kind of transformative impact the Energize project champions across Europe! 🇪🇺

Table 8-1 3rd Newsletter

More information: www.energizcommunity.eu

Co-funded by
the European Union

Co-funded by the European Union, under Grant Agreement n° 101167570. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.